

1. Scanbox API – I am the maintainer and developer.
I have been working on it for the past 6 months.
2. I am the maintainer and developer
3. Creators or maintainers (a few individuals)
4. There is no team responsible for security issues. Since I am in charge of the backend, it is my responsibility to ensure all security issues are resolved.
5. Ruby
6. Ruby on Rails
7. 5 years of experience
8. None
9. When I see a security issue report by another user on support channels, I take time to investigate and find a temporary solution till it is resolved.
10. Maybe 6 out of 10, I try my best to monitor vulnerabilities as the sole maintainer of the project.
11. I am highly aware of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects. That is why I try to keep dependencies up to date as soon as possible.
12. Mostly, I rely on GitHub Dependabot and other developers using the dependency.
13. I usually update dependencies when there is an update available that does not break the live system.
14. I have not quite had a project live for many years to track dependency maintenance.
15. Vulnerable or not, when there is a newer version of a dependency, I check the compatibility with my current project and update it. If there is a long-standing vulnerability I am aware of, I would pick a different dependency to use.

16. It can take up to a month.

17. I have not had an experience with such yet.

18. I would assume it would be a headache, especially if you have little to no knowledge about the other framework.

19. The use of the automated Dependabot, and occasional follow-up on Rails center conversations.

20. No.

21. I normally pin versions in the Gemfile and try to update as early as possible.

22. If the available updates are not compatible with my current project.

23. To use specific versions in projects and update as early as possible.

24. N/A